

Adaptive Power Management for Maximizing Spectral Efficiency and QoS in Cell-Free Systems

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Abstract—This paper investigates power control solutions in the uplink of cell-free systems, focusing on achieving efficient adherence to distinct quality of service (QoS) requirements from terrestrial and aerial users. Such scenarios require innovative power management strategies to maintain robust and balanced network performance. For that purpose, centralized strategies rooted in convex optimization theory are developed to fine-tune the data transmission power of users, with the objective of maximizing the spectral efficiency (SE) while preserving satisfactory minimum data transfer rates among users. In particular, our approach is able to deal with situations in which it is not possible to meet all users' QoS requirements, focusing resources on those that can be fully satisfied while still enhancing service for others as much as possible. This ensures a best-effort service for everyone, optimizing network performance and user experience within existing constraints. The simulations illustrate that our solution strikes a delicate trade-off between excelling in total SE and maintaining elevated user satisfaction levels.

Index Terms—cell-free MIMO, power control, quality of service, spectral efficiency, successive convex optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

As wireless traffic continues to surge, every subsequent generation of cellular networks confronts the enduring challenge of innovation, aiming to accommodate a continuously expanding number of devices while enhancing the spectral efficiency (SE) for each. Within this framework, the deployment of multiple access points (APs) for a confined user group empowers cell-free multiple input multiple output (MIMO) systems to provide unwavering coverage and superior SE. However, a prominent hurdle emerges in uplink cell-free MIMO scenarios: the optimization of power management tailored to users, especially when they present diverse quality of service (QoS) demands. In this sense, cell-free networks present the intricate challenge of formulating strategies for both uplink power control and downlink power allocation. Considering the significant variances in pathloss and shadowing across links, these strategies are pivotal to preclude pronounced performance imbalances [1].

In general, the power optimization issue in cell-free systems has garnered considerable attention and undergone extensive exploration in recent works, catering to a variety of applications and purposes. In [1] policies are presented for uplink power control and downlink power allocation tailored for scalable networks. These policies adeptly balance the trade-off between performance efficiency and user fairness. In [2], the power control issue is also investigated alongside user

scheduling and pilot length optimization. The challenge of optimizing the minimum SE is defined in this setting, and an iterative algorithm, leveraging successive convex approximation methods, is employed to find the solution. Beyond enhancing SE and addressing fairness concerns, power optimization is vital for achieving energy savings and maximizing overall energy efficiency. Recently in [3] the power control problem is designed to optimize global energy efficiency, utilizing a combination of optimization tools, including the classical Dinkelbach method for fractional problems.

While research in radio resource allocation and power optimization is important – especially when ground user equipments (GUEs) and uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs) coexist – surprisingly, none of the works referenced in the present paper have addressed the integration or influence of UAVs, highlighting a gap in the current research landscape. This underscores the need for more comprehensive studies that factor in the dynamics and challenges posed by UAVs in these environments. This coexistence is not merely a matter of network congestion or bandwidth allocation; it introduces a layer of complexity due to the inherent differences in how these two types of devices interact with the network.

Within cell-free systems, where GUEs and UAVs operate concurrently, power optimization for both uplink and downlink has been meticulously examined and elaborated in [4] and [5]. While [4] zeroes in on fairness by tackling the challenge of maximizing the minimum SE, ensuring equitable performance across all users, more recently in [5] a dual focus is adopted, striving not only for fairness but also for the amplification of the total SE within the network. However, none of these studies have delved into addressing the nuances of QoS constraints for distinct groups of users.

In our study, we introduce a tailored uplink power control problem for cell-free MIMO systems. The central objective is to augment the system's total SE while simultaneously accommodating different minimum SE demands for GUEs and UAVs. To solve this intricate challenge, we put forward an iterative algorithm that leverages the principles of successive convex optimization. One of the standout attributes of our approach is its intrinsic adaptability concerning user satisfaction. In real-world scenarios, it is not always feasible to meet the QoS demands for every user due to various constraints, be it network congestion, interference, or physical barriers. Nevertheless, our methodology demonstrates resilience in such

challenging conditions. It not only ensures high performance in terms of total SE but also consistently maintains a high user satisfaction rate. This dual focus, on efficiency and user contentment, is pivotal for contemporary communication systems where user experience is as crucial as technical efficiency.

Moreover, we employ a range of benchmark schemes for a thorough comparative analysis, juxtaposing cell-free scenarios with traditional cellular network models. We meticulously consider classic optimization problems, such as maximizing the aggregate SE and ensuring a baseline minimum of SE, across varied situations for a robust comparison. Distinguishing our work from previously tested approaches, our proposed solution stands out by striking a balance between achieving a high sum of SE and ensuring superior satisfaction levels among both terrestrial and aerial users. This dual accomplishment highlights the efficacy of our method, showcasing its ability to optimize network performance while simultaneously catering to the diverse needs of users in different environments.

II. NETWORK MODEL

Our setup involves a cell-free network comprising K users, each with a single antenna, and L APs equipped with uniform linear arrays of N antennas each. These APs are linked to edge cloud processors, known as central processing units (CPUs), in a flexible manner. The system operates under a time division duplex protocol that unfolds in three phases: initially, users transmit pilot symbols for the APs to estimate the communication channels. Following this, the APs employ these channel estimates to execute channel-matched beamforming for downlink data transmission. In the final stage, users send their uplink data to the APs, completing the communication cycle. In this setup, each coherence block (denoted as τ_c) is segmented into three parts: τ_p channel uses are allocated for uplink pilot signals, τ_d for downlink data transmission, and τ_u for uplink data, with the total coherence block being the sum of these three segments, expressed as $\tau_c = \tau_p + \tau_d + \tau_u$. This paper will focus on analyzing only the τ_p and τ_u periods. APs and users are organized into two distinct groups, \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{K} respectively, and are distributed throughout the coverage area in an uniform manner. The term *users* encompasses both GUEs and UAVs. Therefore, we establish \mathcal{K} as the union of \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{U} , with \mathcal{G} representing the set of all K_g GUEs and \mathcal{U} encompassing all K_u UAVs, making the total number of users K equal to the sum of K_g and K_u , expressed as $K = K_g + K_u$. We introduce \mathcal{A}_k to represent the group of APs that serve a particular user k within the collective user set \mathcal{K} [4].

A. Channel Model

The communication channel connecting user k to AP a is:

$$\mathbf{g}_{k,a} = \sqrt{\frac{\beta_{k,a}}{K_{k,a} + 1}} \left(\sqrt{K_{k,a}} e^{j\vartheta_{k,a}} \mathbf{a}(\theta_{k,a}) + \mathbf{h}_{k,a} \right). \quad (1)$$

In this context, $\beta_{k,a}$ represents the scalar value that encapsulates the channel's path-loss and shadowing effects between the k -th user and the a -th AP. For the GUEs, the large scale coefficient $\beta_{k,a}$ is modeled as in [6], i.e.,

$\beta_{k,a} = 36.7 \log_{10}(d_{k,a}) + 22.7 + 26 \log_{10}(f) + z_{k,a}$ [dB], where $d_{k,a}$ is the distance between user k and AP a , f is the carrier frequency, and $z_{k,a} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 4^2)$ represents the shadow fading. For the UAVs, $\beta_{k,a} = \max\{\text{PL}, 30.9 + (22.25 - 0.5 \log_{10}(h)) \log_{10}(d_{k,a}) + 20 \log_{10}(f)\}$ [dB] is modeled as shown in [7], where PL represents the free space path loss and h the height of the UAV.

The term $\mathbf{h}_{k,a}$, belonging to the complex space, comprises the small-scale fading coefficients for the link between the a -th AP and the k -th user, with each element being independently and identically distributed (i.i.d.) according to a complex normal distribution $CN(0, 1)$. The random phase shift for the direct path is indicated by $\vartheta_{k,a}$, which is uniformly distributed across the interval $[0, 2\pi]$. The steering vector, denoted as $\mathbf{a}(\theta_{k,a})$ for the angle $\theta_{k,a}$ defines the direct path's orientation from AP a to user k . Lastly, $K_{k,a}$ denotes the Ricean K -factor, which quantifies the dominance of the line-of-sight (LOS) component in the received signal.

In general, considering their mobility patterns, UAVs have a distinct advantage over GUEs in achieving LOS connectivity. This inherent characteristic significantly enhances channel quality for UAVs, offering substantial benefits in terms of communication reliability and data transmission efficiency. Such an advantage not only improves the overall user experience but also optimizes network performance by reducing latency and increasing throughput for UAV-connected services. Consequently, the quality of communication links for UAV and GUEs can vary considerably. For more details on channel modeling, as explained previously, for GUEs, the channel model is developed based on [6], while for UAVs, the channel specifications adhere to the guidelines provided by [7].

B. Pilot Transmission and Channel Estimation

The pilot signal received at AP a , $\mathbf{Y}_a \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times \tau_p}$, is: $\mathbf{Y}_a = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sqrt{\rho_k^{\text{pilot}}} \mathbf{g}_{k,a} \boldsymbol{\phi}_k^H + \mathbf{W}_a$, where $\boldsymbol{\phi}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{\tau_p}$ represents the pilot sequence transmitted by user k , and it is designed to have a norm squared $\|\boldsymbol{\phi}_k\|^2$ equal to 1. Furthermore, ρ_k^{pilot} represents the pilot signal power used by the k -th user, while $\mathbf{W}_a \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times \tau_p}$ captures the thermal noise at the a -th AP, with each entry being i.i.d. according to a complex normal distribution $CN(0, \sigma^2)$. By leveraging the pilot sequences, the a -th AP is able to estimate the channel vectors using the relationship $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{k,a} = \mathbf{Y}_a \boldsymbol{\phi}_k$. With the parameters $\{\beta_{k,a}, K_{k,a}, \mathbf{a}(\theta_{k,a})\}_{\forall(k,a)}$ known for every pair (k, a) , the channel's minimum mean squared error (MMSE) estimate, as described in [4], [5], is denoted by $\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{k,a}$, indicating the estimated channel between the user and the AP.

C. Uplink Data Transmission

The data signal received at AP a , \mathbf{y}_a , is expressed as: $\mathbf{y}_a = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sqrt{\rho_k} \mathbf{g}_{k,a} s_k + \mathbf{w}_a$, where ρ_k represents the uplink transmit power and s_k denotes the data symbol for user k , while $\mathbf{w}_a \sim CN(\mathbf{0}, \sigma^2) \in \mathbb{C}^N$ is the additive white gaussian noise (AWGN) vector. For every user k that AP a services, the AP computes the statistic $t_{a,k} = \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{k,a}^H \mathbf{y}_a$ and forwards this to the CPU. The

CPU then aggregates these statistics from all APs serving user k to estimate the data symbol s_k , resulting in the estimated symbol $\hat{s}_k = \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}_k} t_{a,k}$, $k \in \mathcal{K}$ [4]. Taking into account conjugate beamforming and local-MMSE channel estimation, the maximum achievable uplink SE for a user k is

$$\text{SE}_k = \frac{\tau_u}{\tau_c} \log_2 (1 + \text{SINR}_k), \quad (2)$$

where

$$\text{SINR}_k = \frac{\rho_k \left| \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}_k} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{k,a}^H \mathbf{g}_{k,a} \right|^2}{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{K} \setminus k} \rho_j \left| \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}_k} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{k,a}^H \mathbf{g}_{j,a} \right|^2 + \sigma^2 \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}_k} \left\| \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{k,a} \right\|^2} \quad (3)$$

is the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) of user k .

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this section, we turn our attention to the formulation of a power control optimization problem tailored for cell-free uplink data transmission. The central aim is to amplify the aggregate SE throughout the network. However, this optimization is not unconstrained. The mathematical representation of this problem is as follows:

$$\underset{\boldsymbol{\rho}}{\text{maximize}} \quad \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{SE}_k(\boldsymbol{\rho}) \quad (4a)$$

$$\text{subject to } \text{SE}_k(\boldsymbol{\rho}) \geq \text{SE}_k^{\min}, \quad k \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (4b)$$

$$0 \leq \rho_k \leq P_{\max}, \quad k \in \mathcal{K}. \quad (4c)$$

Therefore, beyond the conventional power constraints in (4c), which mandate that the power variables, $\{\rho_k\}_{\forall k}$, must be non-negative and capped at a maximum value of P_{\max} , we additionally face the minimum data rate requirement for each user in constraint (4b). This ensures that every user experiences a baseline level of service quality, further complicating the optimization problem but ensuring a more equitable and efficient network performance.

IV. POWER CONTROL OPTIMIZATION

The inherent non-convexity of problem (4) renders its optimal solution challenging to attain in practical terms. Nonetheless, by adopting the methodology outlined in [5], we can utilize concave and tight inequalities to accurately represent the SE. This approach allows us to devise a centralized and iterative power control solution, effectively circumventing the complexities posed by the non-convex nature of the problem and enabling a feasible and efficient solution. In particular, we use the following inequality for all $x > 0$, $y > 0$, and $\bar{x} > 0$, $\bar{y} > 0$, proved in [8]:

$$\ln \left(1 + \frac{x}{y} \right) \geq \ln \left(1 + \frac{\bar{x}}{\bar{y}} \right) + \frac{\bar{x}}{\bar{y}} \left(2 \frac{\sqrt{\bar{x}}}{\sqrt{\bar{x}}} - \frac{x+y}{\bar{x} + \bar{y}} - 1 \right), \quad (5)$$

where we define for problem (4) the following terms: $x = \rho_k q_k$, $y = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K} \setminus k} \rho_j u_{k,j} + t_k$, where: $q_k = \left| \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}_k} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{k,a}^H \mathbf{g}_{k,a} \right|^2$,

$u_{k,j} = \left| \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}_k} \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{k,a}^H \mathbf{g}_{j,a} \right|^2$ and $t_k = \sigma^2 \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}_k} \left\| \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{k,a} \right\|^2$. Then, the SE expression can be approximated to a local tight concave lower bound ($\widetilde{\text{SE}}$) as shown in (6), where $\eta_k = \frac{\rho_k^{(l-1)} q_k}{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{K} \setminus k} \rho_j^{(l-1)} u_{k,j} + t_k}$. By substituting $\widetilde{\text{SE}}$ in (4) we can address the resulting power control issue using conventional convex optimization techniques, as outlined in the SCO-based power iterative algorithm (SCOPIA), described in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 SCO-based Power Iterative Algorithm (SCOPIA)

- 1: **Input:** $\{\mathcal{A}_k\}_{\forall k}$, and start from an initial feasible point $\boldsymbol{\rho}^{(0)}$, $l \leftarrow 1$;
 - 2: **Output:** Data power vector $\boldsymbol{\rho}$;
 - 3: **loop**
 - 4: Utilize the approximations $\{\widetilde{\text{SE}}_k\}_{\forall k}$ and $\boldsymbol{\rho}^{(l-1)}$ in the desired optimization problem;
 - 5: Solve the obtained power control via CVX to obtain $\boldsymbol{\rho}$;
 - 6: Set $\boldsymbol{\rho}^{(l)} \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\rho}$, and $l \leftarrow l + 1$;
 - 7: **end loop**
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In Algorithm 1, line 1 takes a starting feasible point $\boldsymbol{\rho}^{(0)}$. Our method for determining the initial point in practical applications is straightforward: we generate it randomly within the set power limits. Next, the process involves iteratively updating the power control vector by solving a convex optimization problem using the outcome from the previous step. Specifically, at step 4, by applying approximations $\{\widetilde{\text{SE}}_k\}_{\forall k}$ for all k and the previous iteration's point $\boldsymbol{\rho}^{(l-1)}$, the problem becomes concave. Then, at step 5, we use the CVX solver [9] to find a new point $\boldsymbol{\rho}$, which serves as the input for the next iteration. The convergence of this algorithm is ensured by its design [5]. Each iteration aims to improve the objective function, leading to a local optimum due to the concavity of the problem. Thus, we achieve a locally optimal solution by iteratively solving approximated convex problems. In practical terms, the described *loop* (lines 3-7) should continue iterating until the convergence of $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ is achieved, as determined by the following criterion: $\left\| \boldsymbol{\rho}^{(l)} - \boldsymbol{\rho}^{(l-1)} \right\|^2 / \left\| \boldsymbol{\rho}^{(l)} \right\|^2 \leq \epsilon$, where ϵ is an acceptable tolerance for the convergence of $\boldsymbol{\rho}$.

It is crucial to emphasize that the SCOPIA procedure offers a versatile approach to power control and is not strictly limited to addressing problem (4). Rather, its design inherently accommodates any issue characterized by a convex nature and reliant on $\widetilde{\text{SE}}$ expressions. This inherent flexibility means that Algorithm 1 is equally adept at tackling a range of power control challenges. As investigated in [5], it can be employed to solve the power control problem aiming to maximize the sum of unconstrained $\widetilde{\text{SE}}$ s. Similarly, issues related to optimizing the minimum $\widetilde{\text{SE}}$ can also be addressed effectively using that approach.

While the SCOPIA procedure is inherently versatile in addressing power control challenges, it is essential to understand its limitations, especially concerning problem (4). A significant hurdle arises from the minimum SE constraints inherent to this problem. Finding a suitable starting point or “feasible point” can be particularly challenging due to these constraints. Moreover, ensuring the QoS demands are met for every user becomes a complex task.

$$SE_k(\rho) \geq \widetilde{SE}_k(\rho) = \frac{\tau_u}{\tau_c \times \ln 2} \times \ln(1 + \eta_k) + \frac{\tau_u}{\tau_c \times \ln 2} \times \eta_k \times \left(2 \frac{\sqrt{\rho_k}}{\sqrt{\rho_k^{(l-1)}}} - \frac{\rho_k q_k + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K} \setminus k} \rho_j u_{k,j} + t_k}{\rho_k^{(l-1)} q_k + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K} \setminus k} \rho_j^{(l-1)} u_{k,j} + t_k} - 1 \right) \quad (6)$$

It is well-understood in network theory that a user's geographic location can significantly influence their service quality. In many instances, depending on where a user is situated, the conditions might be particularly unfavorable for satisfying QoS demands. Such constraints can lead to situations where, despite the algorithm's best efforts, it might not always provide the desired results. Consequently, when employing the SCOPIA procedure exclusively to address problem (4), one must anticipate potential outage events. These outages can become increasingly frequent, especially when individual users have stringent minimum SE requirements or when interference escalates due to the presence of UAVs.

In general, the primary challenge with outage events lies in the fact that only a small subset of users often experience difficulties in meeting their minimum requirement levels. This not only disrupts the user experience for this minority but can also have cascading effects on network efficiency and overall user satisfaction. Addressing these isolated instances is crucial not just for the affected individuals, but for maintaining the robustness and reliability of the entire system. Therefore, to enhance the effectiveness of the SCOPIA procedure and ensure a more consistent problem-solving experience, we introduce a more resilient approach to proactively mitigate the occurrence of disruptive events. This methodology aims to find solutions even when certain users may not meet their minimum SE requirements. It is imperative to note that while our method may not guarantee every single user's SE requirements, it is designed to ensure that the overwhelming majority of users have their rate demands adequately satisfied. This approach prioritizes overall network stability and user satisfaction, offering a pragmatic solution where perfect outcomes might not always be feasible. We introduce our solution as Algorithm 2, termed the network outage-free adaptive intelligent logic (NO-FAIL). This solution is based on the $\{\text{SINR}_k\}_{\forall k}$ expressions, where users utilize the maximum transmission power.

Algorithm 2 Network Outage-Free Adaptive Intelligent Logic (NO-FAIL)

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1: Input: Initialize  $\{\widetilde{\text{SINR}}_k\}_{\forall k}$ ;
2: Output: Data power vector  $\rho$ ;
3: loop
4:   try:
5:     Solve problem (4) using SCOPIA for set  $\mathcal{K}$ ;
6:   catch:
7:      $\hat{u} \leftarrow \arg \min_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \{\widetilde{\text{SINR}}_k\}_{\forall k}$ ,  $\rho_{\hat{u}} \leftarrow P_{\max}$ , and  $\mathcal{K} \leftarrow \mathcal{K} \setminus \hat{u}$ ;
8:   end
9: end loop when  $\mathcal{K}$  is an empty set

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The core concept of our approach is to initially address the primary problem (4) using the SCOPIA procedure, as indicated in line 5. If, for any reason, it is infeasible to meet the QoS requirements of all users in set \mathcal{K} , our method then pinpoints

a user likely obstructing a feasible solution. This identification takes place in line 7 with a low-complexity approach, where the user with the lowest SINR value is singled out and then removed from set \mathcal{K} in line 8, meaning their satisfaction becomes non-essential. To further optimize their SE level, this user is allocated maximum power. While this approach may increase the interference caused in the remaining users, it provides a best-effort service to the worst users instead of giving zero rate to them. As long as set \mathcal{K} retains members, we launch renewed efforts to tackle problem (4), honing in on a select subset of users to achieve the stipulated SE constraints.

Conclusively, our proposed solution sets its baseline performance at a scenario where all users engage in full power allocation. Specifically, in challenging circumstances where the network cannot maintain the desired QoS for any of its users, our strategy systematically omits users from the optimization process. Over time, this method will lead to a state where all remaining users in the network operate at their peak transmission power. This ensures that, even under strenuous conditions, the network attempts to optimize user experience to the best extent possible.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Characteristics Taken into Account for the Simulations

The essential simulation parameters can be found in Table I.

TABLE I: Main parameters used in simulations

Parameter	Value
Number of APs	100
Number of GUEs	15
Number of UAVs	5
SE_{GUE}^{\min}	0.60 bits/s/Hz
SE_{UAV}^{\min}	0.90 bits/s/Hz
P_{\max}	150 mW
AP distribution	Horizontal: uniform; Vertical: 10 m
GUE distribution	Horizontal: uniform; Vertical: 1.65 m
UAV distribution	Horizontal: uniform; Vertical: 22.5 – 300 m
AP antenna array	Four-element ULA
Thermal noise	-174 dBm/Hz
Carrier frequency	1.9 GHz
Bandwidth	20 MHz

We consider a square area of 1 km² and we executed 1,000 Monte Carlo realizations for every solution analyzed. Additionally, we posit two distinct network configurations: a cell-free system based on user-centric clustering and a cellular setup utilizing MIMO technology [10]. In our simulations, we also incorporate a variety of benchmark schemes for comprehensive comparison and analysis. First, we tackle the challenge of maximizing the aggregate of SEs without minimum SE constraints (Max sum-SE). Next, we focus on the task of improving the minimum SE (Max min-SE). Lastly,

we consider a more straightforward approach — the Naive solution — where power allocation for SEs is kept simple, always utilizing the maximum transmission power.

B. Discussions and Analysis of the Results

Fig. 1 illustrates the convergence trends of the analyzed solutions, emphasizing the cumulative SEs, when utilizing the SCOPIA procedure for power profile refinement. In this context, this depiction provides insights into the efficiency and adaptability of SCOPIA in achieving efficient power configurations. In these first results, as expected, there is a notable trade-off in the total sum of SEs to ensure equity within the system. Specifically, observe the pronounced disparity between the Max min-SE and the Max sum-SE solutions, highlighting the inherent tension between optimizing performance and ensuring fairness. An interesting observation is that the Naive approach, despite its simplicity, can offer reasonable performance with respect to the total SE. Yet, significant improvements are achieved when power optimization is applied.

Fig. 1: Convergence curves for various power control problems utilizing the SCOPIA-based methodology and Naive solution.

Fig. 2 shows the SEs experienced by users. First, we highlight a substantial enhancement in the minimum SE for cell-free scenarios compared to traditional cellular networks, as evidenced by the yellow curves. This proves that the distributed architecture of cell-free networks is particularly advantageous, offering significant potential for solutions designed to maximize the minimum SE. For other approaches that primarily aim to maximize the sum SE (i.e., Naive, Max sum-SE and NO-FAIL solutions), it is observed that while the SE peaks are attained by cellular networks, on average, the SE performance is more favorable in cell-free networks. This indicates that although cellular networks may reach higher SE values at their peak, cell-free networks consistently maintain better average SE. Particularly for our proposed solution, as illustrated by the black curves, there is a noticeable decrease in performance compared to methods that optimize for the sum SE without considering minimum SE constraints (Max sum-SE). Additionally, our approach displays distinct vertical segments directly aligned with the minimum SE thresholds

outlined in Table I. This pattern reflects our deliberate effort to adhere to QoS demands. However, this adherence incurs in a trade-off that invariably affects the cumulative sum SE.

Fig. 2: CDF curves: comparing the minimum SE between the proposed solution (NO-FAIL) and various benchmark schemes.

To gauge the satisfaction levels associated with the solutions examined in this study, Fig. 3 presents the distribution of users whose needs fell short of the minimum SE criteria outlined in Table I. These users, whose requirements were not satisfied, are designated as SE-Shadow Users. Firstly, it is noteworthy that in solutions primarily aimed at maximizing the sum SE (i.e., Naive, Max sum-SE and NO-FAIL solutions), the satisfaction levels among UAVs tend to be significantly higher compared to GUEs, even under stringent SE demands. This is largely attributed to the enhanced channel quality experienced by aerial users, which facilitates better performance outcomes. Indeed, this behavior is not mirrored in the Max min-SE solution due to its intrinsic characteristics. The Max min-SE approach is designed to ensure fairness across the network by equalizing the SE levels among all users. Consequently, meeting the SE requirements for UAVs within this framework would necessitate elevating the SE levels of all GUEs to match those of the UAVs. This presents a significant challenge, given the distinct channel conditions experienced by GUEs, making it impractical to impose the same QoS standards on GUEs as those applied to UAVs.

Moreover, an important insight from Fig. 3 is that the count of SE-Shadow Users in cell-free networks is significantly lower than in cellular networks. The enhanced coverage, attributed to the distributed AP architecture, plays a crucial role in elevating user satisfaction levels. This distributed approach in cell-free networks ensures more users are within optimal coverage zones, thus meeting their SE criteria more effectively. In quantitative terms, our analysis of the proposed solution in cell-free networks reveals that over 90% of the time, all UAVs meet their minimum SE requirements. Furthermore, in more than 80% of scenarios, only one GUE falls short of achieving the desired QoS demand. These results are significantly higher when compared to other solutions. This clearly illustrates that our proposed solution not only achieves commendable

Fig. 3: Distribution graphs showcasing the amount of GUEs and UAVs that fall below the minimum SE constraints, termed SE-Shadow Users, across the (NO-FAIL) proposed solution and various benchmark schemes.

performance in terms of total SE but also maintains markedly higher rates of user satisfaction relative to benchmark solutions. This balance between efficiency and user satisfaction is a key strength of our approach.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work explored centralized strategies for managing power in the uplink of cell-free systems, particularly in environments where GUEs and UAVs operate simultaneously. In general, centralized solutions, including our proposed convex optimization-based approach, offer robust performance with high efficiency. Yet, their applicability can become limited as the network user base expands, leading to significant scalability challenges. To overcome this hurdle, our future direction involves crafting distributed machine learning methodologies that proficiently address QoS requirements while simultaneously enhancing the network’s scalability capabilities.

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